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CONTENTS

BUDGETING BASED ON THE BALANCED SCORECARD SYSTEM IN STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING.....	8
Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabievna	
TURIZM SOHASIDA TARJIMA NAZARIYASINING O'RNI.....	13
Bahronova Charos Mirabbos qizi	
THE ROLE OF ESG PRINCIPLES AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CORPORATE SOCIAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS.....	16
Shokhrukh Abdisalimovich Muratkosimov	
A COMPARATIVE SEMANTIC FIELD ANALYSIS OF "BENEFIT" ACROSS ENGLISH AND UZBEK CULTURES.....	23
Mohira Husanovna Divanova	
ROSSIYA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA DEPOZIT OPERATSIYALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS JIHATLARI.....	30
Rahimov Akmal Matyaqubovich	
USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES AGAINST CYBER THREATS IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR.....	37
Nuratdinov Xushnid Begzadovich, Erejepov Kewlimjay Kaymatdinovich	
PUL-KREDIT SIYOSATI INSTRUMENTLARIDAN FOYDALANISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH..	42
A.A. Ismailov	
"O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AJNING AMALIY IQTISODIY HOLATI TAHLILI VA OPSIONLARNI ANIQLASH.....	48
Bobojonova Zarnigor Shokirovna	
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR AUTOMATED SKIN DISEASE DIAGNOSIS FROM DERMOSCOPIC IMAGES.....	56
Nazirova Elmira Shodmonovna, Abdusalomova Shokhista Boboyor qizi	
STRATEGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINANCIAL MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL AND GREEN TRANSFORMATION.....	61
Muftaydinov Mansur Kiyomidinovich	
TOURISM POTENTIAL OF UZBEKISTAN AND FINANCIAL FACTORS FOR ITS DEVELOPMENT.....	68
Bau Long	
CASH FLOWS OF "TERRITORIAL ELECTRIC NETWORKS" JSC: COMPREHENSIVE ACCOUNTING ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO IMPROVEMENT.....	75
Djuraev Davlat Djonibekovich	
MONETARY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	78
A.A. Ismailov	
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR OF REGIONS.....	83
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
KNOWLEDGE STRATEGY AND ITS SYSTEM OF INDICATORS IN STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING.....	89
Pardaeva Shakhnoza Abdinabievna, Pardaeva Zulfizar Alimovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE REGIONAL DYNAMICS AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LABOR MIGRATION.....	95
Mukhtorbek Rahimboyev, Alibek Normurodov	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA KREDIT RISKLARNI BAHOLOVCHI TIZIMLARNI ISHLAB CHIQUISH. MIJOZ SCORE MODEL VA QARORLARNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	104
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP IN ESG IMPLEMENTATION: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	111
Khusenova Mekhrangiz	

FORMATION OF MEDICAL TOURISM CLUSTERS IN THE REGION	115
Yusupova Mehribon O'ktamovna	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE INTEGRATION OF SCADA AND ERP SYSTEMS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	120
Abdullaev Munis Kurbonovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN IMPLEMENTING GREEN PUBLIC PROCUREMENT AND LESSONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	125
Ruzimurodova Charos Ural qizi	
AGROTECHNICAL AND INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING GRAIN PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY	129
Turayeva Gulizahro	
MINERALOGICAL OCCURRENCE OF RARE METALS IN THE INGICHKA DEPOSIT AND DEVELOPMENT OF TUNGSTEN EXTRACTION TECHNOLOGY	133
Shodiyev Abbos, Dononov Jasur, Safarov Gulomjon	
STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP COOPERATION IN THE GREEN ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN	140
Zukhra Bakhramovna Abdikarimova	
TIME MANAGEMENT IN THE CRAFT ECONOMY: STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMIZING THE TIME RESOURCES OF INDIVIDUAL PRODUCERS	148
Feruza Nazrillaevna Israilova	
DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL SUSTAINABILITY GOALS	154
Muminova Mokhchekhra	
FEATURES AND FACTORS OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	160
Ibodullayeva Malohat Sirojiddin qizi	
MECHANISMS FOR POVERTY REDUCTION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	165
Dauletmuratov Adilbay Mirzabaevich	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF ENVIRONMENTAL AUDITING AT ENTERPRISES BASED ON A RISK-ORIENTED APPROACH AND DIGITAL EVIDENCE	171
Abdullayev Khurshidjon Nazrullo o'g'li, Khurshidjon Abdullayev	
INTEGRATION MECHANISMS OF DIGITAL ECONOMY TECHNOLOGIES INTO REGIONAL GOVERNANCE SYSTEMS	176
Kurbonova Malika Ahmad kizi	
DEVELOPMENT OF A LOGICAL-LINGUISTIC MODEL OF THE KOREAN NOUN CATEGORY AND CREATION OF A PREFIX AND AFFIX DATABASE.....	181
Yendirboyeva Zumrad Zohidjon qizi	
THEORETICAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF MANAGING STATE SHARES IN BUSINESS ENTITIES	186
Akmaljon Valijonov	
ENSURING OBJECT SECURITY AND ANALYZING INFORMATION SECURITY BASED ON NEURAL NETWORKS.....	190
Babayazov Saidbek Po'latovich, Sultamuratova Dilnoza Gulmuratovna	
FUNDAMENTAL METHODS FOR IDENTIFYING AI-GENERATED DATA IN ACADEMIC AND ONLINE PUBLICATIONS USING MACHINE LEARNING AND NLP MODELS.....	196
Abdullaev Munis Kurbonovich, Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli	
QUALITY ASSURANCE OF NON-AUTOCLAVED AERATED CONCRETE WITH THE ADDITION OF CMC (CARBOXYMETHYL CELLULOSE)	204
Pulatova D.G., Akhundjanov K.A.	
INTEGRATION MECHANISMS OF DIGITAL ECONOMY TECHNOLOGIES INTO REGIONAL GOVERNANCE SYSTEMS	210
Kurbonova Malika Ahmad kizi	

IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS SOLUTIONS	215
Shamsiyev O'ktam Sayfitdinovich	
ASSESSING THE SOURCES AND QUALITY OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH USING THE SOLOW MODEL.....	222
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF BANKING SYSTEM DIGITALIZATION	228
Suyunov Feruz, Ergashov Firdavs, Norqulov Habibullo	
HARDWARE-AWARE PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF YOLOV8 FOR REAL-TIME APPLICATIONS: GPU ACCELERATION WITH TENSORRT AND AN ANALYTICAL FPGA COMPARISON.....	232
Ulugbek Tursunaliyev, Bakhromjon Tulkinov	
DEVELOPMENT OF SPATIAL INFORMATION MODELS OF TERRITORIAL DEVELOPMENT TAKING INTO ACCOUNT ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN AND THE ARAL REGION)	241
Reymova Gulmira Polatovna	
LEADERSHIP STYLES AND QUALITY ASSURANCE CULTURE IN UNIVERSITIES.....	248
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
SOCIO-ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND INCENTIVE SYSTEMS IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR.....	256
Zafar Ibragimovich Xakimov	
SOCIOLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF NEGATIVE AESTHETIC EVALUATION UNITS DENOTING PHYSICAL APPEARANCE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.....	260
Qalandarova Shaxzoda Qurbonboy qizi	
REMITTANCE INFLOWS AND THE SUSTAINABILITY OF ECONOMIC GROWTH: A TIME-SERIES ANALYSIS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	265
O. B. Gimranova	
FORECAST INDICATORS, PROSPECTS, AND OUTCOMES OF DEVELOPING THE MECHANICAL ENGINEERING INDUSTRY THROUGH GREEN INVESTMENTS.....	271
Xursandov Komiljon Maxmatkulovich	
FEATURES AND FACTORS OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	276
Ibodullayeva Malohat Sirojiddin qizi	
FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	282
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich	
THE DIGITAL GASTRONOME: HOW TECHNOLOGY CONNECTS TOURISTS, RESTAURANTS, AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS	286
Freshta Qayoumi	
THE REPRESENTATION OF RESTRICTED LEXICON IN FRENCH LITERARY WORKS	290
Gulnoz Akhmedova	
RESEARCH ON THE TRANSMISSION MECHANISMS AND IMPLEMENTATION PATHS OF SHANDONG PROVINCE'S "SILVER ECONOMY" DEVELOPMENT EXPERIENCE IN THE FERGANA REGION	294
Zhang Zhe	
APPLICATION OF NET PRESENT VALUE ANALYSIS TO SHORT-TERM PERSONAL FINANCIAL DECISIONS	299
Akhunova Elena Anvarovna	
ECONOMIC OPPORTUNITIES FOR INCREASING EMPLOYMENT THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES IN KHOREZM REGION	307
Azadova Gulnoza Sardorbekovna	
DEVELOPMENT TRENDS AND INSTITUTIONAL FEATURES OF THE STOCK MARKET IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	313
Nargiza E. Jiyanova, Diana D. Qurbaniyazova	
MODELING AND FORECASTING THE SCIENTIFIC PUBLISHING ACTIVITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (A CASE STUDY OF SCOPUS DATA).....	321
Ozoda B. Sakieva	

YELLOW TOURISM: CONCEPTUAL CONTOURS, SPECTATORIAL LOGICS, AND THE POLITICS OF JOYFUL MOBILITY	326
Samiev Siroj, Ochilova Guli	
SHAKESPEARE'S CREATIVE METHOD: ADAPTATION, COLLABORATION, AND THEATRICAL REFINEMENT	334
Mirzakhidova Nozima Ulugbek kizi	
THE IMPACT OF TOURISM ON UNESCO SITES: THE CASE OF SAMARKAND	338
Samiev Siroj, Kakhramanova Maftuna	
MODERN METHODS FOR ASSESSING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY UNDER CONDITIONS OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	344
Meyliyev Farrux Ikrom o'g'li	
INTEGRATION OF ESG PRINCIPLES INTO THE CORPORATE GOVERNANCE SYSTEM OF STATE-OWNED ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN: KEY BARRIERS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS.....	349
Jumadullaeva Durdona Shukhrat qizi	
COMPARATIVE ADVANTAGES OF LOCAL NATURAL AND ECONOMIC POTENTIAL AND THEIR EFFECTIVE USE UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE CONDITIONS	357
Madenova Elmira Nizamatdinovna	
IDENTIFICATION OF FACTORS INFLUENCING RETAIL SALES	362
Markova Mariya Stanislavovna, Pooja	
APPLICATION OF MARKETING APPROACHES AND PRINCIPLES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM	377
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	

APPLICATION OF MARKETING APPROACHES AND PRINCIPLES IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article examines the main aspects of marketing education, its social and psychological characteristics that determine its behavior in the market, consumer, analysis of supply and demand, search for ways to balance them, identification of unused opportunities in the consumer market, and the specific characteristics of educational services — the main product of the education system.

Keywords: Marketing, education system, demand, opportunity, improvement, concept, quality.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются основные аспекты маркетингового образования, его социально-психологические характеристики, определяющие его поведение на рынке, у потребителя, анализ спроса и предложения, поиск путей их балансирования, выявление неиспользованных возможностей на потребительском рынке, а также специфика образовательных услуг — основного продукта системы образования.

Ключевые слова: Маркетинг, система образования, спрос, возможность, совершенствование, концепция, качество.

INTRODUCTION

Education and science are considered among the important areas of socio-economic development in Uzbekistan. In recent years, special attention has been paid to improving the system of continuing education and aligning it with the needs of the modern labor market. The requirements of the international labor market, the acceleration of integration processes, digitalization, and technological changes in industry have increased the need to train competitive middle-level specialists with modern qualifications and practical skills. As a result, the vocational education system has been gradually improved, and the formation of a professional education system that meets international standards has become one of the important directions of educational reforms.

The essence of these reforms is to develop human resources in a new quality and format, to form practical qualifications in young people that are required by domestic and foreign labor markets, and to strengthen their social responsibility and civic engagement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

An analysis of the existing literature on marketing principles in the education system shows the need to improve modern marketing principles, brand promotion methods, and a flexible approach to consumer demands. Regarding marketing principles, the works of R. G. Ibragimov and other scholars should be noted. Among them, we can include such famous scientists as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Baer.

While the research in the field of marketing conducted in our country for many years is based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to recognize the scientists who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R. Ibragimov, Yo. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva, and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass monitoring methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The emergence of a market for various attractive educational services and products in the education system of our country has posed a completely new task for entities providing educational services and producing educational products: a new, scientifically based approach to education management is needed. This approach consists of offering an integrated package of services among participants in the educational services market.

Marketing in education performs three functions in the economy:

1. The special importance of education in economic development. Modern technologies determine the upper limits of the economic development of society. However, their spread depends on the educational system and the level of the population. Consequently, marketing is associated with the dissemination of advanced educational ideas.

2. The development of education as a branch of the economy and an institution of every state. The wider the range of educational services and products, the higher their quality and accessibility, and the higher the standard of living of society. Consequently, the development of the education system directly depends on the marketing tools used.

3. Educational institutions are, as a rule, financed from budgets and funds received through the collection of fees for educational services. The limited possibilities of budgets in a transitional economy determine the development of the marketing of paid educational services.

Given the increasing competition in the market of educational services and products, to assess potential demand, one should resort to marketing research methods. The purpose of marketing research is to identify prospective educational needs, assess their satisfaction, test hypotheses, and predict consumer behavior. In this regard, it makes sense to apply the methodology of conducting marketing research to analyze educational needs. Therefore, the second problem that needs to be solved is to conduct marketing research and study market prospects.

By activating the classic elements of marketing, market segmentation can be implemented, services can be promoted using marketing communications, and the problem of matching the educational needs of the target audience with the capabilities of the educational institution can be solved.

The educational program, which is being implemented to ensure the quality of education, uses marketing tools to bridge the gap between reality and desired educational outcomes. It proposes the following:

Table

Educational Programs Implemented to Ensure the Quality of Education¹

1

Provides significant changes in interaction with the external environment:	The following provide fundamental changes in the internal environment:
Openness of the operating system in the services sector;	Ease and success of training;
Focusing education on public needs;	Realization of the subjective position of all participants in the educational process;
Adequacy and timeliness of measures taken in response to environmental change;	Developing tolerance among participants in the educational process;
Actively seek sources of support from social partners and additional resources (financial, informational, material and technical, didactic, etc.);	Implementing effective educational technologies;
Repetition in the educational process of socio-economic relations that dominate society.	The optimal ratio of various types of student activity, his intellectual, emotional and physical activity;
	Students have the opportunity to choose their educational path and educational content (except for the state standard component).

The stage of preparation for significant changes requires the establishment of a marketing department in professional educational services. Because the market for educational services is expanding day by day. The emergence of private educational institutions creates strong competition, which, in turn, creates a demand for marketing and marketing research.

1 Source: Author's development.

The term “marketing” comes from the English word “market”, which literally means “market activity”. This term appeared in the economic literature of the United States at the end of the 19th century. Its emergence and use were associated with the need to improve the management system of existing activities in the market. Marketing as an independent field of activity and science emerged at the beginning of the 20th century. The famous marketing theorist Philip Kotler developed the semantics of the concept of “marketing”, its principles, functions, elements of marketing activity, its goals, and the marketing mix. The goal of the marketing system is to determine the maximum possible consumption of goods and services, achieve maximum consumer satisfaction, offer the widest possible choice, maximize the quality of goods and services, and expand the range of its consumers.

Marketing principles are a set of basic conditions and requirements that reveal the fundamental essence of marketing. Based on the essence of marketing, the following principles are considered fundamental in marketing activities:

- “The consumer is the central focus of marketing activity.”
- “It is not about selling manufactured products, but about making products that are sold.”
- “With the creation of a product, it is also necessary to create its consumer.”
- “A differentiated approach to commodity markets is needed.”
- “A company should earn its own profit and reputation only by satisfying consumer demand.”

Approaches to the principles include:

- Producing what the consumer needs.
- Entering the market not with goods and services, but with tools that solve consumer problems.
- Establishing the production of goods and services after consumers have studied the demand.
- Accelerating the launch of activities.
- Using a targeted, programmatic, and integrated approach to achieve set goals.
- Applying tactics and strategies at the right time to adapt the product to market demands, and effectively applying marketing throughout the process until the product reaches the consumer.
- Strengthening the market position of the product by providing the company with long-term effective communication.
- Taking into account the social and economic factors of production at each stage of the life cycle of goods and services.
- Developing a business plan based on the market.
- Coordinating supply and demand by establishing cross-sector integration.
- Actively working to strengthen the company’s competitive advantages and image.

Thus, marketing principles are rules that define the basic requirements for the meaning of marketing.

In modern marketing, “We do not offer goods or services, but solve consumer problems!” To solve what problems does a person resort to offering educational services and products? This issue has not yet been fully addressed within the existing education system, although the educational problems of the individual are quite rare. Marketing activities are mainly based on the general principles of marketing, but due to the specific characteristics of the product, they have a number of differences. Thus, marketing in education is a complex of research, planning, implementation, and monitoring of developed programs, the implementation of which involves voluntary interaction with target markets in order to achieve the goals of the educational institution.

The main thing in marketing education is the analysis of the consumer, his social and psychological characteristics that determine his behavior in the market, the analysis of supply and demand, the search for ways to balance them, and the identification of untapped opportunities in the consumer market. The specificity of marketing in education is primarily associated with the specific nature of the main product of the education system — educational services. Educational services satisfy the needs of the individual (end user), group (employers), and public (state).

The intangibility of a service means that it cannot be demonstrated; that is, it cannot be seen, tasted, touched, heard, or smelled before receiving it. The lack of tangible characteristics of a service before purchasing it increases the level of uncertainty in purchasing. To reduce this, customers look for “signals” of service quality.

The inseparability of a service means that it cannot be separated from its source, regardless of whether the service is provided by a person or a machine. Since the consumer is always involved in the production of the service, interaction with the supplier (teacher) is a separate area of service marketing. The teacher’s ability to communicate with students affects their performance. The second characteristic feature of the inseparability of services is their participation in the provision of services to other consumers. When one person uses the service, students in the audience are present. Their behavior determines the level of satisfaction of people with the service. Therefore, the task of the service provider is to ensure that users of some educational services do not interfere with other consumers in obtaining quality information.

Variability in service quality means that its quality can vary greatly depending on who, when, where, and

how it is provided. It is very difficult to monitor the quality of services, especially educational services. The quality of the service provided by one teacher varies depending on his physical appearance and mood during communication with students. The administration of the educational institution should constantly monitor the level of satisfaction of students with the quality of the educational process through questionnaires and monitoring of learning outcomes.

The fragility of a service means that it cannot be stored for later sale or use. If the demand for it is stable enough, durability does not pose any specific problems. However, if demand is subject to various fluctuations, the educational institution will face problems, for example, the problem of the number of teachers. It is characteristic of educational services that educational information is prepared and stored in handouts, books, cassettes, and electronic disks. However, it should be noted that knowledge quickly becomes obsolete.

New conditions for the provision of educational services have simultaneously necessitated the restructuring of the activities of educational institutions. Today, the education market has reached a stage where supply and demand are becoming more balanced; differentiated demand for educational services has been formed; the infrastructure of the educational services market has developed; and the need to use marketing approaches to ensure the sustainable development of educational institutions has increased.

Thus, there is a need to introduce a marketing approach in the education sector at the present time. In such a situation, public organizations using marketing tools can win the competition and take their rightful place in the market: they study supply and demand, balance the "product portfolio" of educational services and products, offer prices that meet solvency and demand, and conduct a communication policy.

The market for educational services and products is a system of supply and demand relations of forms and means of satisfying educational needs, based on a set of conditions that ensure the provision of these services offered by educational institutions, in close contact with the consumer and producer of educational services and products offered by educational institutions, methodological support, and material base.

The market activity of educational institutions is at an early stage; therefore, the type of educational market can be defined as a purely competitive market. Research shows that there should be a monopolistic competitive market in the educational space. It is such a market that requires the development of marketing activities for the intermediary activities of licensing bodies that control the reputation of educational institutions and the quality of the services offered.

The basis of marketing is the following concepts: the concept of improving educational production; the concept of improving products — educational services; the concept of intensifying commercial efforts, such as advertising, contracts, application research, and paid educational activities; the concept of consumer orientation; and the concept of socio-ethical marketing, namely the social protection of the consumer.

The concept of improving production in the field of education is associated with two interrelated trends: an increase in the number of schools with various and non-state forms of ownership; expanding the list of educational services by introducing additional services, including paid services, in existing state educational institutions. The presence of these trends gives potential consumers of educational services the opportunity to choose an educational institution for educational services based on price and quality, and creates competition in the educational services market. The concept of improving the product or service in education implies a shift in focus to the content of education. This becomes especially relevant in connection with the introduction of the state educational standard. In order to ensure the social protection of a graduate, an educational institution must have high-quality training not only for a promising profession and work, but also for life in market conditions.

Competition in the educational services market has led many educational institutions, especially those providing paid educational services, to the need to apply the concept of increased commercial activity: various types of attracting potential consumers are widespread — advertising and professional information.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, the principles and concept of marketing require that consumers of educational services and products be in the center of attention. In order for an educational institution to be in demand, it must, first of all, study educational needs and, secondly, satisfy them and be better than other educational institutions. This can be achieved if the educational needs of the population are met. But the state, being not only the main investor in education, but also the guarantor of the quality of education, also sets its own requirements for itself — to educate not only a professional, but also a citizen who can actively live in a socio-market economy. The dialectical relationship of the interests of the state, the consumer of educational services, and educational institutions is reflected in the concept of social and ethical marketing.

Modern marketing is designed for a comprehensive and systematic approach to the management of an educational institution and the quality of the result — the level of graduate training. Marketing is carried out

through marketing research, promotion of educational services to the final consumer, and financial support for education.

References

1. Mirziyoyev, Sh. M. (2017). *The rule of law and the protection of human interests are the key to the country's development and the well-being of the people*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan.
2. Mirziyoyev, Sh. M. (2017). *We will build a great future with our brave and noble people*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan.
3. Mirziyoyev, Sh. M. (2020). Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. *Xalq so'zi*, January 26, 2020.
4. Azimovna, M. S. (2022). Formation of psychology and pedagogy as interdisciplinary sciences. *Formation of Psychology and Pedagogy as Interdisciplinary Sciences*, 1(9), 20–23.
5. Musayeva, S., & Usmanov, F. (2022). Ways to develop marketing activities in tourist organizations. *Science and Innovation*, 1(A5), 84–88.
6. Azimovna, M. S., Ilkhomovna, U. D., & Shokhrukhovich, U. F. (2022). Issues of improving productivity competition in agriculture. *Online Scientific Journal of Innovation in Social Sciences*, 51–53.
7. Azimovna, M. S., Ilkhomovna, U. D., & Shokhrukhovich, U. F. (2022). The role of marketing in increasing the economic efficiency of service enterprises. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*.
8. Azimovna, M. S., Ilkhomovna, U. D., & Shokhrukhovich, U. F. (2022). The concept of a correct marketing policy in trade and service enterprises. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*.
9. Musayeva, S. (2022). Studying the organization of advertising activities of goods at "Samarkand Tea Packaging Factory" JSC. *Science and Innovation*, 1(A6), 185–192.
10. Musayeva, S. (2022). Prospects for the development of "Stekloplastik" LLC activity in the conditions of the market economy. *Science and Innovation*, 1(A6), 539–546.
11. Azimovna, M. S., Ilkhomovna, U. D., & Shokhrukhovich, U. F. (2022). Importance and characteristics of brand choice in services. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 1–3.
12. Musaeva, Sh. A. (2023). *Marketing research*. Samarkand: Publishing and Creative Department of "STAR-SEL" LLC.
13. Musaeva, Sh. A. (2022). *Integrated marketing communication*. Samarkand: "Mahorat" Publishing House.

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